

POSTBUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF BLADE-STIFFENED FIBRE COMPOSITE PANELS

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Abstract

The capabilities of advanced finite element modelling packages such as MSC/NASTRAN and COSMIC/STAGS to predict the onset of buckling and subsequent postbuckling behaviour for a composite blade-stiffened panel with stiffener run-outs, have been investigated. Presented are different modelling techniques such as linear static, linear buckling, geometric nonlinear analysis and 2D to 3D element coupling, used for the analysis of postbuckling panels. The analytical predictions of the behaviour have been compared with experimental results obtained from a box beam test rig in a four point bend test. It is concluded that the prediction of the bending-buckling response associated with "run-out" stiffeners can be investigated using advanced numerical programs, and the ultimate failure mechanisms can be effectively investigated in detail with 2D to 3D element coupling techniques.

Keywords: Postbuckling, compression, finite element, nonlinear analysis, stiffened panels.

1. INTRODUCTION

The safe operation of carbon epoxy stiffened panels in their postbuckled state is an area of increasing importance as composites are progressively introduced into primary aerospace structures. The incorporation of composites into commercial airframes is driven by the need to increase structural efficiency and minimise operational costs. The design of a postbuckling blade-stiffened panel representative of commercial aircraft skin construction, but manufactured as a co-cured component from unidirectional T300 / 914 carbon fibre / epoxy preimpregnated tape and stiffened with blade shaped stringers is the topic of the research work presented.

The phenomenon of postbuckling of stiffened panels has traditionally been studied in panels where the skin and stringers are uniformly loaded. This aspect of composite structures has been investigated by a number of authors including Ashwini¹, Stein², and Reddy³. The case of structures experiencing a bending-buckling response has received less attention, and is the subject of this paper.

A feature of the panel used for this investigation is the manner in which the stiffeners "run-out", or terminate. Often the design is such that the stiffeners need to terminate to avoid interference with surrounding structure. A common method of overcoming this detail design problem is to run-out or taper the stringer height where necessary. A consequence of selecting such a configuration is

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that only the skin can be loaded directly, and the run-out of the stiffeners introduces an eccentricity in the panel's neutral axis, which results in bending deformations from the onset of a compressive loading.

The laminate design for the panel was constrained by the criterion that the stacking sequence for the stiffeners should be symmetrical. This resulted in a skin that alternates between being a symmetrical and unsymmetrical laminate, as shown schematically in Figure 1. This departure from conventional symmetrical composite construction is necessary, as the stringers are manufactured by extending the top three skin plies to the sides of the blade-stiffeners. This design allows the stiffeners to become effectively integral, the consequence of this is the skin lay-up must alternate across the panel between each stringer.

As the behaviour of the panel is complicated by the bending-buckling behaviour, simple closed form analytical solutions do not exist. A study has been undertaken using the general purpose finite element codes MSC/NASTRAN and COSMIC/STAGS to investigate this bending-buckling response and the outputs have been compared with experimental results. Linear static and linear buckling analyses have been performed, together with geometric nonlinear analyses to investigate the behaviour. A local three dimensional model incorporating 2D to 3D element coupling has been included to investigate the through thickness stresses arising in the postbuckled state.

Figure 1. Blade-stiffened panel ply configuration.

2. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

2.1. Description of Testing Configuration.

Tests were performed on the blade-stiffened panels by utilising the box beam test rig shown in Figure 2 to introduce compression into the panel. The four point bend rig consists of an aluminium three bay box beam structure used as the bend specimen with dimensions: 3000 mm in length, 150 mm in width and 600 mm in height. The aluminium box beam is supported in a steel rig, to which the load jacks and reaction legs are attached, so the system is self reacting. The jack loading is reacted by the two reaction legs that are positioned in line with two central ribs separating the box beam's three bays; in this way a constant bending moment is introduced into the middle bay, where the test panel is located.

The middle bay of the structure has a detachable skin to allow for different panels (such as the blade-stiffened panel) to be interchanged via a mechanical fastening system. A consequence of

the box beam arrangement is that the clamping configuration only allows loading through a uniform thickness, thereby requiring the stiffeners to be run-out to the skin thickness at each end.

Figure 2. Box beam test rig with blade-stiffened panel affixed.

2.2. Description of Finite Element Model

The finite element model of the blade-stiffened panel was constructed from 3150 two dimensional linear shell elements. The model did not include detail of the clamping area. The carbon / epoxy lay-up was described by the composite capabilities in NASTRAN and STAGS, which models the plies and laminate properties consistent with the assumptions of classical laminate theory.

A compressive loading of 200 N/mm was applied to the short edges of the panel as a distributed line loading, with the opposite edge restrained to react this load. Clamped edge boundary conditions were applied to the panel, with fixed edges on the unloaded sides and kinematic constraints, known as Multi-Point Constraints (MPC's) in NASTRAN and partial constraints in STAGS, to ensure that the loaded edges were uniformly shortened under the compressive loading, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Loading and boundary conditions applied to stiffened composite panel.

2.3. Results

Linear static and linear buckling analyses were performed using both NASTRAN and STAGS. The results from the linear static analysis showed an out-of-plane displacement of 9.5 mm for both finite element codes. The linear buckling solution predicted the lowest eigenvalue / buckling factor of 0.358 using NASTRAN and 0.343 with STAGS for an ultimate load of 200 N/mm. The results from

STAGS displayed the lowest eigenmode to correspond to ten half-wavelengths in the skin between the stiffeners, whilst the eigenmode predicted with NASTRAN appeared unrealistic and did not agree with the mode predicted from STAGS. The linear buckling eigenmode portrayed only buckling of the skin without the global bending present due to the eccentricity in the neutral axis of the panel.

A geometric nonlinear analysis in NASTRAN incorporating a Newton-Ralphson convergence strategy was performed with an initial imperfection to represent the first linear buckling mode predicted with STAGS. The imperfections were provided by offsetting nodes (grids in NASTRAN) at the location of the peak buckling amplitudes. The magnitude of the imperfections were one percent of the physical skin thickness.

The out-of-plane contour plot for the nonlinear analysis shown in Figure 4, represents a panel that is undergoing bending, which causes the greatest deformation, and buckling which is indicated by the small irregularities in the response. The contours describe a structural response that is symmetric about a diagonal; this behaviour is to be expected, as the stiffeners have a low torsional stiffness⁴. Small irregularities in the contours are present due to the skin alternating between a symmetrical and unsymmetrical ply stacking sequence.

Results from the moiré fringe pattern was used as a qualitative assessment of the out of plane displacement pattern. The moiré fringe pattern displayed the same number of buckles as predicted in the nonlinear analysis with NASTRAN. The non-uniformity of the displacement field for the moiré fringe pattern shown in Figure 4, is attributed to the light source not being parallel over the width of the panel.

Figure 4. Out-of-plane displacement contours for a geometric nonlinear analysis, subject to initial imperfections, and shadow moiré fringe pattern

The results from back to back strain gauges in the skin section of the blade-stiffened panel are plotted in Figure 5. The strain gauges were located in the two centre skin sections, 26 mm away from the panels transverse center line, as this position was predicted to be near a buckle peak with the finite element model. The results from the linear and geometric nonlinear analyses displayed good agreement with experimental results up to buckling point, with both numerical analyses and experiment predicting strains in the order of -1100 microstrain. The nonlinear analysis compared favourably with the experimental results early in the postbuckled region, however an accurate strain comparison was not obtained well into the postbuckled regime. The experimental and numerical results consistently showed buckling to occur at approximately 34% of the ultimate load.

Figure 5. Back to back strains in the skin section for applied loads, and the corresponding predicted finite element results.

2.4. Discussion

For the configuration considered, a linear eigensolution is sufficient to estimate the buckling load factor, however it does not represent the real response which sees bending and buckling in the panel. The nonlinear analysis predicted the postbuckled deformation accurately when compared to the moiré fringe pattern, however strain gauge results in the postbuckled regime did not compare so favourably with the geometric nonlinear results. A reason for this poor correlation can be attributed to the fact that the four point bend test introduces curvature as well as compression on the unloaded edges of the test panel. The curvature of the box-beam could be represented in the finite element model by applying a distributed moment on the loaded edges. The results from an investigation using the nonlinear capabilities of STAGS is under investigation and the results will be presented at a later date.

The failure of the panel initiated at the tips of the stiffener run-outs due to interlaminar shear. The area was predicted as the critical region in the finite element model, which showed the 45 degree plies at the tips of the stiffeners to be the points for first ply failure. However the 2D model was not able to predict interlaminar shear strains with accuracy near free edges. For this reason the panel failed premature of the numerically predicted results. A detail model of run-out can be investigated using a linear static analysis, as the stiffener run-out area is in the linear range, even though the remaining structure is postbuckling.

3. LOCAL 3D SKIN STIFFENER INTERFACE STRESS ANALYSIS

3.1. Reason for 3D Stress Analysis

A validated technique is needed to allow the 3D stress state to be represented in order to obtain an appreciation of the failure mechanisms involved in the critical areas of the blade-stiffened panel. The use of fibre composite laminates adds to the complexity of the material behaviour and therefore the modelling required to represent the local structure. Presented here is a generic technique for the coupling of 2D to 3D elements for a local area for which a local 3D stress state can be represented in a postbuckled structure.

To model the complete blade-stiffened panel with finite elements, based on 3D elasticity theory, is computationally very expensive. A more realistic approach has been suggested by Card and Starnes⁵. They propose that only a relatively small domain of the structure has to be modelled with 3D finite elements, while the bulk part of the structure can be modelled with plate finite elements. Coupling the sub-domains requires a specialised modelling technique, because plate finite elements and solid finite elements are incompatible in their elastically supported degrees of freedom. Transition elements⁶, kinematic constraints with plate degrees of freedom being dependent⁷, and kinematic constraints with solid degrees of freedom being dependent. The last method has been chosen for further investigation because it allows significant changes in mesh density between the plate finite element model and the solid finite element model.

3.2. Coupling Technique

The degrees of freedom on adjacent plate and solid finite element nodes can be mathematically coupled with kinematic constraints. The corresponding equations can be derived in two steps (refer Figure 6). Step 1 defines the kinematic relations between the imaginary node (i) and the physically existing plate nodes (n2) and (n3). Step 2 defines the kinematic relations between the existing solid element node (n5) and the imaginary node (i). Combining the two steps results in the kinematic relation between the plate element nodes and the solid element nodes. The kinematic relations between the degrees of freedom on node n2, n3 and i can be expressed with the bilinear shape functions of the QUAD4 element⁷ (refer Equation 3.1 & 3.2).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \phi_2 &= x \cdot (1-y) & (3.1) & & u_i &= \phi_2 \cdot u_2 + \phi_3 \cdot u_3 & (3.2) \\
 \phi_3 &= x \cdot y & & & v_i &= \phi_2 \cdot v_2 + \phi_3 \cdot v_3 \\
 & & & & w_i &= \phi_2 \cdot w_2 + \phi_3 \cdot w_3 \\
 & & & & j_{xi} &= \phi_2 \cdot j_{x2} + \phi_3 \cdot j_{x3} \\
 & & & & j_{yi} &= \phi_2 \cdot j_{y2} + \phi_3 \cdot j_{y3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Kirchhoff's basic plate theory⁹ states that the displacements of an arbitrary point on a plate can be expressed in terms of the displacements of the middle surface and the rotations of the surfaces normal to the middle surface. This leads to a relation between the degrees of freedom on node i and node n5 (refer Equation 3.3).

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_5 &= u_i + h \cdot \phi_{yi} & (3.3) & & u_5 &= \phi_2 \cdot u_2 + \phi_3 \cdot u_3 + h \cdot \{ \phi_2 \cdot \phi_{y2} + \phi_3 \cdot \phi_{y3} \} & (3.4) \\
 v_5 &= v_i - h \cdot \phi_{xi} & & & v_5 &= \phi_2 \cdot v_2 + \phi_3 \cdot v_3 - h \cdot \{ \phi_2 \cdot \phi_{x2} + \phi_3 \cdot \phi_{x3} \} \\
 w_5 &= w_i & & & w_5 &= \phi_2 \cdot w_2 + \phi_3 \cdot w_3
 \end{aligned}$$

Substituting Equations (3.2) into Equations (3.3) results in the kinematic relation between the degrees of freedom on the solid element node n5 and the degrees of freedom on the plate element nodes n2 and n3 (refer Equation 3.4).

The coupling technique has so far been implemented for the NASTRAN elements QUAD4 and HEXA. Good results have been achieved for standard load cases such as pure bending and pure torsion. The coupling technique has limitations in displacement fields with a strong curvature along the interface line between the plate elements and the solid elements. In that case non-structural stress concentrations occur. Employing finite elements with C₁ conformity may reduce this effect.

Figure 6. Coupling nodal degrees of freedom

Figure 7. Local 3D finite element model

3.3. Results

The postbuckling analyses performed in Section 2, identified critical stress levels in the skin-stiffener junction area. A 3D finite element model representing a critical local area has been generated and was incorporated into a global 2D finite element model (refer Figure 7.). Boundary displacements computed in the postbuckling analyses of Section 2 have been used as input for a stress analysis of the local three dimensional finite element model. Geometric stiffening has so far been neglected. The results show that only minor peel stress occurs in the skin stiffener area investigated. The results also show significant interlaminar shear stress in the skin under the stiffener and in the lower part of the stiffener (refer Figure 8.). This implies that a failure of the panel in this area will most likely occur through a delamination of the laminate.

Work undertaken by Hachenberg¹⁰ and Jones¹¹ shows that the material behaviour of epoxy resins is nonlinear. This material nonlinearity must be taken into account. Several ASTM rail shear tests of $[0,90]_s$ laminates have been numerically simulated. A nonlinear material law has been derived for that laminate in an iterative process (refer Figure 9.). This material law may be incorporated into the finite element model of the local skin stiffener area.

Figure 8. Through thickness shear stress

Figure 9. Material law for $[0,90]_s$ laminate

4. CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the point of buckling can be accurately determined for a postbuckling carbon/epoxy stiffened panel with 2D finite element methods. A technique to model a local area of the blade-stiffened panel has been presented to enable detail on the precise nature of the failure mechanisms to be determined. These numerical models are useful tools for achieving an understanding of the behaviour of postbuckling composite panels, and thus the maximum performance and efficiency in future aerospace structures.

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